

THE CONTRIBUTION OF UZBEK SCHOLAR AHMEDOVA L.T
TO FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. *This thesis examines the contribution of Uzbek scholar Axmedova Laylo Tolibjonova, Doctor of science in Pedagogy, Professor, Department of “Teaching English Language Methodology and Educational Technologies”, Faculty OF “English Philology”, paying closely attention to her system of teaching Foreign Languages in Uzbekistan, methodical features of using supporting and Foresight technologies in teaching English, which she had suggested to University students and the understanding importance of psychology to foreign language acquisition -new proposed technology ,which will make the learning process more effectively and easy to learn for University students.*

Keywords. *Foreign Language Teaching, Technologies, Analyses, Methods, The supporting technology, SWOT, Delphi, Psychology.*

Introduction. Language is the main strengths of human being, the valuable tool from which, we can communicate with each other, express our feelings and emotions, along with the way of knowing our needs. Language is the greatest treasure, the bridge through we can explore the world, being acknowledged about present, getting information about outside world. Language plays a crucial role in shaping who we are as an independent individual. As we mentioned, language is considered to be a bridge to getting knowledges and information both in our culture and abroad, being more precisely, implementing foreign languages to our life can ensure the key success almost in all spheres of our life, whether professional and developmental. That is way, it is so pivatal to be fluent in both

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languages native and foreign, due to the fact that non-native language can potentially assist to recognize his native language better, which plays in helpful method for mastering other languages. This statement had been proven by psychologists and sociolinguistics. Teaching foreign languages had succeeded a great achievements and had become a field of continuous educational research. In addition with European scholars, Uzbek scholars had investigated and accomplished many improvements in this field of studies such as Ahmedova L.T, Jalolov J.J, Mahkamova G.T and Sattorov.

Main part. Ahmedova Laylo Talibjanovna had conducted several investigations into methodology and pedagogy with several methods, technologies and techniques with detailed theory and application into foreign language acquisition, her contribution to teaching foreign languages highly estimated and valued in our country. One of great works connected with the implementation of different technologies into teaching process, one of them are known as supporting technology, the technology based with the usage of large-block presentation with the help of modern teaching aids such as tables, graphs, notes in this method of teaching, teacher can engage students into independent studies, at the same time increasing their stimulation into learning process with the mean of structuralized information that includes different notions, unfamiliar words with simple form. The supporting technology techniques that can be implemented into teaching foreign languages include “Prognostic chart” and “Moral Qualities of characters”. This kind of techniques will increase their knowledges into reading and speaking. The Prognostic chart will benefit them into abilities of comparing, anticipating and systemizing the information they will take during the reading procedure. The Moral qualities will focus on comparing circumstances, in terms of what they should do, what not. This technique is the form of generalizing information with emotions, because of the morality. Another technology, that Laylo Talibjanovna had devoted to examine is “Foresight technology”, which was published at international journal. Firstly, this technology was related to business purposes, in the late 50s, but this form of technology is used in many of spheres such as

pedagogy, chemistry, physics and biology. Laylo Talibjanovna had suggested using this technique into education, especially into teaching Foreign Languages because, it can develop their predictive, critical, logical thinking and oral competencies. She supposes, that this technology may include the methods, that have in common with SWOT analyses and Delphi method. The Delphi method is dedicated to solutions that should be taken throughout brainstorming procedure, while SWOT analyses is based on evaluating factors of an object into four categories: Strengths, Weaknesses Opportunities and Threads. Turning to the implementing two methods into Foresight technology, she had proposed the Delphi can help to evaluate a group of experts as well as analyzing the problem, while the SWOT can supply a description of what should be done according to four analyses. One more field of research, Laylo Talibjanovna had examined is the importance of psychology to foreign language acquisition. According to her statement in the textbook, there had been stated that, language is not just a tool for communication, but this is also the weapon of our brain functioning.

Conclusion. Ahmedova Laylo Talibjanovna's research has made significant contributions to foreign language teaching by integrating modern technologies and pedagogical methods. Her use of supporting technology and techniques like the Prognostic Chart and Moral Qualities of Characters, enhances student engagement and cognitive development. Overall, her research provided innovative and practical approaches to improve foreign language instruction and learning outcomes.

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